

Policy brief – Deliverable 8.3

Paving the way for inclusive labour markets under the European Pillar of Social Rights

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PATHS2INCLUDE

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**European Labour Markets Under Pressure –
New knowledge on pathways to include persons
in vulnerable situations**

Title: Policy brief: paving the way for inclusive labour markets under the European Pillar of Social Rights

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[PATHS2INCLUDE](#) is a 3-year research project funded by Horizon Europe that investigates 1. the multi-dimensional aspects of discrimination, 2. policies that could reduce inequalities and promote social inclusion in European labour markets and 3. risk factors of vulnerability that may arise in the future of work. The research focuses on three key labour-market processes: recruitment; career paths; and exit from working life, giving particular attention to labour-market participation at the intersection of gender, ethnicity, age, health, disability, and care responsibilities.

1. Introduction

The [European Pillar of Social Rights](#) includes twenty principles and rights to support well-functioning and fair labour markets and welfare systems, structured around three categories: equal opportunities and access to the labour market, fair working conditions, and social protection and inclusion. To implement these principles, the [Action Plan](#) sets out a number of EU actions and three EU headline targets to be achieved by the end of 2030 in the areas of employment, skills, and social protection.

One of the targets aims to increase the employment rate to at least 78% (of the population aged 20 to 64) by 2030. To achieve this goal, the European Commission is striving to promote greater participation in the labour market by as many working-age individuals as possible, by removing existing barriers and reaching out to groups with fewer opportunities (European Commission, 2021). Nevertheless, the latest European Commission's Employment and Social Developments report highlights that one-fifth of the working-age population, around 51 million people, are currently outside the labour market (European Commission, 2025a).

This persistent exclusion is harmful to the EU economy and societal unity as it may lead individuals into roles beneath their skills level, contribute to workplace underperformance, discourage labour market participation and misallocate talent, eroding social cohesion and diminishing both civic engagement and community development (OECD, 2025).

Expanding the labour force by increasing the participation of underrepresented groups enhances productivity and strengthens the resilience of labour markets to demographic shifts. This reduces pressure on pension systems, healthcare, and public finances, making it a vital step towards boosting the EU's long-term competitiveness and preparedness for future economic and social challenges.

In June 2025, the European Commission launched a public consultation on the new European Pillar of Social Rights Action Plan that would be finished by the end of 2025. In response, this EU policy brief draws on PATHS2INCLUDE findings to fill in gaps in data and provide policy recommendations for promoting inclusive labour markets, with the aim of implementing the European Pillar of Social Rights principles. The recommendations are especially relevant for the following Pillar Principles: 1. Education, training and life-long learning, 2. Gender Equality, 3. Equal opportunities, 4. Active support to employment, 6. Wages, 9. Work-life balance, and 10. Healthy, safe and well-adapted work environment.

2. Main findings

The following section discusses the main findings of the PATHS2INCLUDE research, highlighting persisting issues in the context of labour market outcomes of groups in vulnerable situations.

2.1. Education and skills development can offset effects of disadvantages

The EU target of adults participating in training every year is set for at least 60% by 2030. However, by 2022 only 39,5% of adults were participating in learning activities (excluding guided on-the-job training) each year (European Commission, 2025b). For low-qualified adults this rate only reached 18%. PATHS2INCLUDE findings confirm the importance of reaching the higher training target by showcasing the strong correlation between higher education levels and increased labour market participation and employment. In particular, tertiary education emerged as a key factor that can partially mitigate the impact of structural disadvantages related to gender and health on labour market attachment (Valls et al., 2025). In addition, education became increasingly important for navigating the post-pandemic labour market that is shaped by digitalisation and flexible work arrangements, disproportionately benefiting those in higher-skilled occupations.

Moreover, research findings highlight that for individuals with health limitations¹, labour market attachment is closely related to their skills, even if they stay in the same occupation (Lipowska & Palczyńska, 2025). This indicates that enhancing skills may improve their employment situation without needing to change occupations. Since people with health limitations may have fewer opportunities to change occupations, policies supporting the development of digital and social skills could help reduce the negative effects of health limitations on labour market participation.

2.2. Gender inclusive labour markets

By 2030, the European Commission aims to at least halve the gender employment gap compared to 2019 (European Commission, 2021). PATHS2INCLUDE findings, however, show that women, and particularly those with dependents, are generally less likely to be active in the labour market than men, differences that most likely reflect the continuing influence of gendered caregiving

¹ The variable 'health limitation' is measured by the respondent's self-assessment of whether he/she is limited (in "activities people usually do") by any on-going physical, mental or emotional health problem, including disease or impairment, and old age. Consequences of injuries/accidents, congenital conditions, etc., are all included. Only the limitations directly caused by or related to one or more health problems are considered. In this context, disabilities are considered as being the consequence of health problems, and limitations due to disabilities are taken into account as being caused by health problems (Eurostat, 2021).

responsibilities (Valls et al., 2025). Moreover, research results show a gendered parenthood penalty, with mothers—especially single mothers—facing significant disadvantages in the recruitment process (Buttler et al., 2025). Despite an overall increased female labour force participation, gender wage gaps and barriers to career advancement remain significant.

The research also emphasises the economic vulnerability of women in retirement. Men and women display similar retirement intentions but when other risk factors, such as caregiving responsibilities, health limitations and low socio-economic status, are taken into consideration, women are more likely than men to indicate the intention to retire early (Vasile et al., 2025). This often goes with fragmented career paths and lower earnings resulting in lower retirement savings which might lead to financial gender gaps and insecurity in older age.

2.3. Persistent gaps in data availability

As part of the research, EU and national surveys were analysed to assess their ability to identify at-risk groups in the labour market. The findings highlight the difficulty of identifying these groups, the discrimination they may face, and their poor labour market integration, due to several factors such as limited sample sizes or lack of specific questions (Valls et al., 2024). Although some surveys incorporate questions designed to capture data on at-risk groups or phases of life, the scope and generalisability of the results is often limited. This lack of comprehensive data poses a crucial challenge in accurately assessing the impact of employment policies on at-risk groups. A more comprehensive data collection would enable EU policy makers to better understand the challenges faced by at-risk groups and effectively tailor interventions to promote inclusive and equitable employment opportunities across different stages of the working life, as well as prepare policies to decrease vulnerability in the future of work.

2.4. Intersecting disadvantages shape labour market exclusion

PATHS2INCLUDE research shows that being at risk of labour market exclusion is not only based on individual characteristics such as gender, age, education, or migrant background, but often relates to contextual characteristics and their interplay and intersection throughout the life course of people. For example, women with health limitations living in households with dependents faced especially high barriers to labour market attachment (Valls et al., 2025). These factors combine to create specific challenges and barriers to labour market entry, stability, and progression. Policies designed to strengthen labour market attachment need to look at the intersectional nature of disadvantage, as one-size-fits-all approaches are likely to be inadequate considering such complexity. Alternatively, inclusive measures need to target overlapping vulnerabilities, supporting not only older workers or individuals with health limitations, but also recognising how these characteristics intersect with gender, caregiving responsibilities, and education.

2.5. Discrimination in recruitment remains prevalent across Europe

EU law sets minimum requirements on the equal treatment of persons regardless of sex, ethnic or racial origin, disability, religion or belief, age and sexual orientation.² However, our research findings confirm that mothers and ethnic minorities continue to experience systemic biases across Europe which limits equal access to employment opportunities, aligning with outcomes of the latest report on the application of the Directives (European Commission, 2021b). Across all countries included in our research, immigrants faced significantly lower hiring chances, regardless of their language skills or education origin indicating potential nationality-based discrimination (Rogstad et al., 2025). Another group particularly subject to hiring discrimination are single mothers (Buttler et al., 2025). The analysis focused specifically on the organisational features that shape this discrimination, finding that comprehensive organisational support and inclusive hiring practises can contribute to a more diverse workforce (Rogstad et al., 2025). Collective recruitment panels, flexible work arrangements, concrete diversity measures (such as inclusive hiring procedures, mentoring or buddy programmes) a transparent assessment of soft skills, and training opportunities are some of the initiatives identified to reduce hiring discrimination.

2.6. Activating older workers may increase inequalities

Encouraging older workers to postpone retirement may increase inequalities as not all workers have equal opportunities to adjust their timing of retirement and extend their working life. For workers in vulnerable situations, disadvantages tend to accumulate over the life course, making a disproportionate impact on their quality of life in older age. An analysis of SHARE data reveal gender, household structure, health, education, and wealth as central drivers of exclusion of older workers, often interacting in complex ways (Alecu et al., 2025). For example, there is a clear correlation between health limitations and the economic vulnerability of older workers in Europe: workers facing significant health challenges indicate the highest levels of mental and physical exhaustion after work, worry more often about their future economic situation and report more difficulties in making ends meet (Vasile et al., 2025). Moreover, both economic constraints and health limitations influence the timing of exit of older workers: financial stability allows for greater control over one's retirement timing in contrast to low income, which leads to extended employment or early retirement with insufficient resources (Vasile et al., 2025). This issue will become increasingly challenging as pension reforms are eliminating a clear

² Council Directive [2000/78/EC](#) of 27 November 2000 establishing a general framework for equal treatment in employment and occupation and Council Directive [2000/43/EC](#) of 29 June 2000 implementing the principle of equal treatment between persons irrespective of racial or ethnic origin.

statutory retirement age and making income security more dependent on the duration of one's ability to work. The COVID-19 pandemic already introduced new vulnerabilities, particularly affecting older women's risk of involuntary exit (Alecú et al., 2025).

Addressing the challenges that ageing populations face in the workforce requires a targeted support for longer working lives and a stronger focus on creating health-promoting workplaces for older workers. Policies that promote the extended participation of older workers such as health screenings, active living and ergonomic approaches can help keep aging workforces healthy and engaged. The Council Directive 89/391/EEC harmonises occupational health services across EU member states for better health and safety standards, although its implementation varies at a national level (Hämäläinen, 2020).

2.7. Wealth can mitigate vulnerability

Another target of the European Commission is to reduce the number of people at risk of poverty by at least 15 million by 2030 (European Commission, 2021). The research found that the economic context in which individuals live can impact labour market participation and retirement decisions. For example, a higher level of wealth is linked to a reduced likelihood of being excluded from the labour market (Alecú et al., 2025). The region where one lives matters as well, for example, women living in a wealthier region tend to have a higher probability of employment (Vivoli et al., 2024). Wealth appears to mitigate other vulnerabilities, such as poor health and gender, significantly reducing their negative effects among individuals with greater economic resources. To protect against (in-work) poverty and inequalities, minimum wages play an important role. However, after a substantial decline in 2022, real wages started to grow in the EU from the second half of 2023 though remain below pre-pandemic level (European Commission, 2025b).

2.8. Care responsibilities shape gendered inequality in the labour market

PATHS2INCLUDE research found people with caregiving responsibilities to be among the most vulnerable in terms of labour market participation (Vivoli et al., 2024). Care responsibilities, particularly informal care within families, present a significant challenge to activation, hiring, employment, and extended working lives, especially for women. Caregiving responsibilities can lead to fragmented employment trajectories resulting in lower retirement savings and greater financial insecurity in older age, especially for women.

Results from another part of the research show a gendered parenthood penalty where mothers, especially single mothers, face significant disadvantages in hiring processes (Buttler et al., 2025). This is particularly the case when women are applying for demanding jobs. The research also found that care-based discrimination occurs less in organisations offering flexible work arrangements and/or that have implemented diversity policy measures, which particularly benefits single mothers.

2.9. The future of work presents both opportunities and challenges for vulnerable groups

Digitalisation offers opportunities for flexibility and accessibility, but it also introduces barriers and exacerbates existing inequalities for at-risk groups. First, widening skill gaps, as a result of digitisation and automation, risk deepening existing wage inequalities which would disproportionately affect less educated and medium-skilled workers (Valls et al., 2024). Second, some gender disparities persist, with the widespread use of non-voluntary remote work further exacerbating stress and role conflict among mothers (Beckel & Fisher, 2022). Third, older workers seem to be more likely to retire early and experience the negative consequences of work intensification due to technological developments (Valls et al., 2024). In conclusion, the impact on carers, people with disabilities, older workers and migrant workers underlines the need for targeted policy responses (see also Magda & Krząkała, 2025).

3. Policy recommendations for shaping inclusive labour markets

The following key measures emerged from PATHS2INCLUDE findings and should be considered closely in the review of the Action Plan on the European Pillar of Social Rights, with the aim to make labour market measures more inclusive in policy and practice. These are relevant for both EU-level actions (policy, data and funding) as well as national and sub-national actions to support the implementation of the European Pillar of Social Rights, namely for public authorities, statistics institutes, Public Employment Services and Non-Governmental Organisations providing employment support, as well as social partners. EU funding programmes can also support these changes, either through financing direct services which can benefit European workers (e.g., through the ESF+) or through transfer of innovation and transnational exchanges (e.g., through the EaSI programme for employment and social innovation) (Rossenbacker & Gosme, 2025).

- **Invest in skills and training programmes tailored to the needs of vulnerable populations.** Instead of merely focusing on providing training to highly skilled individuals, training and education initiatives should be available to all at-risk groups, including people with health limitations, to mitigate the negative effects of existing disadvantages on their attachment to the labour market.
- **Invest in comprehensive data collection** to capture the employment dynamics and experiences of at-risk groups in a way that allows for cross-country comparisons and intersectional analysis. This comprehensive data collection involves expanding existing surveys to include more detailed information on socio-demographic characteristics, health and disabilities, and migration trajectories, in addition to factors that may influence employment outcomes, such as caregiving responsibilities. Longitudinal studies with larger

sample sizes allow for monitoring the effectiveness of policies over time and understanding the complex interactions between the various factors that influence employment decisions and outcomes in the present and the future of work.

- **Design policies with an intersectional approach** by targeting overlapping vulnerabilities stemming from individual characteristics, including age, health limitations, gender and caregiving responsibilities. By recognising and addressing the complex interplay of individual vulnerabilities and regional economic conditions, future labour market interventions can more effectively promote inclusion and social cohesion across the EU.
- **Ensure the full implementation and compliance with Directives 2000/78/EC** on equal treatment in employment and occupation and 2000/43/EC of 29 June 2000 implementing the principle of equal treatment between persons irrespective of racial or ethnic origin.
- **Encourage and support organisations to adopt concrete, actionable diversity policy measures** such as inclusive hiring practices, mentoring programmes, and diversity management training while engaging managers in diversity efforts to mitigate biases in recruitment processes. Policy makers should also create (financial) incentives and support mechanisms to drive such workplace changes.
- **Expand flexible work arrangements** to facilitate work-life balance for parents and carers, as well as prevent care-based discrimination of (single) mothers. Moreover, interventions that enhance flexibility, inclusion, and support for care responsibilities, can additionally protect older workers. The uptake of these flexible and inclusive work arrangements (e.g., through public incentives or regulatory frameworks) should be particularly supported in sectors where discrimination is most pronounced.
- **Establish health-promoting workplaces** for enabling older workers to remain in employment longer and reduce their economic vulnerability. Support the implementation of Council Directive 89/391/EEC to mainstream occupational health services across Europe.
- **Ensure adequate minimum wages**, in a way that satisfies the needs of workers and their families in the light of national economic and social conditions, whilst safeguarding access to employment and incentives to seek work. Workers have the right to fair wages that provide for a decent standard of living. In-work poverty shall be prevented. All wages shall be set in a transparent and predictable way according to national practices and respecting the autonomy of the social partners.
- **Implement adequately paid leave for workers with caregiving responsibilities** enabling them to take time off work without losing income and thereby reducing financial stress and allowing better balance between caregiving duties and employment.

Taken together, these results underscore the importance of intersectional and adaptive policy responses: while structural vulnerabilities persist, well-designed interventions in the context of the European Pillar of Social Rights, particularly those that enhance flexibility, inclusion, and well-being, can play a decisive role in improving labour market outcomes of people in vulnerable situations.

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